

Teacher Perceptions of the Use of Generative AI Tools in ESL Classrooms: A Review of Studies

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Abstract: *The integration of Generative Artificial Intelligence (GenAI) tools in English as a Second Language (ESL) classrooms has gained increasing attention in recent years. While these tools offer numerous advantages, such as personalized learning, automated feedback, and enhanced student engagement, their effectiveness largely depends on teachers' perceptions and willingness to integrate them into their teaching practices. This literature review examines existing research on teacher perceptions of GenAI in ESL classrooms, focusing on both the potential benefits and the challenges associated with its implementation. The review explores themes such as pedagogical applications, teacher attitudes, technological barriers, and ethical concerns. Findings suggest that while many educators recognize the potential of GenAI for improving instructional efficiency and student autonomy, concerns related to accuracy, digital literacy, and the risk of over-reliance on AI-generated content persist. Additionally, a lack of institutional support and teacher training remains a significant barrier to widespread adoption. The review highlights gaps in current research, particularly in non-Western ESL contexts, and emphasizes the need for further studies on professional development programmes and long-term impacts of the integration of GenAI in language learning.*

Keywords: *English as a Second Language (ESL), Generative Artificial Intelligence (GenAI), ChatGPT, Technology Enhanced Language Learning (TELL), Mobile Assisted Language Learning (MALL), Computer Assisted Language Learning (CALL)*

1. INTRODUCTION

Changes of the world, related to any field, has a capacity in affecting the field of Education. Thus, areas such as Technology Enhanced Language Learning (TELL), Mobile Assisted Language Learning (MALL) and Computer Assisted Language Learning (CALL) were developed. Added to the evolving environment of educational technology, Generative Artificial Intelligence (GenAI) has evolved, as a transformative tool in the language teaching and learning contexts.

Highly developed algorithms and models as ChatGPT, Microsoft Copilot, Gemini and related models which are capable of generating human-like texts, images and other multimedia content originate from given prompts are generally referred as GenAI tools. One of the earliest definitions to AI given by Grewal, as cited in [1], is “the science and engineering of making intelligent machines”, implying that intelligence can be modelled by a machine. This definition got broadened gradually interpreting AI as intelligent agents that learn from the environment and perform actions [2]. By 2023, it has evolved reflecting advancements in technology, changes in

understanding and aiming shifts on focus. Oxford English Dictionary [3] defines it as "the theory and development of computer systems able to perform tasks normally requiring human intelligence, such as visual perception, speech recognition, decision-making, and language translation."

English as a Second Language (ESL) teaching and learning contexts can utilise these tools as practical applications that assist in preparing personalised learning materials, automating lesson plans and tools that provide instantly tailored feedback on the use of language and for many other language learning/teaching needs. As an example, certain teaching prompts in an ESL speaking classroom such as authentic, personalised conversations, related to different scenarios can be conveniently generated using an AI tool as ChatGPT, which saves the whole time spent in browsing or searching several books or other materials. Such innovative uses of GenAI tools reflect a broader shift in modern language teaching, where the emphasis is increasingly placed on learner-centered, technology-enhanced instruction.

One of the critical factors that requires attention in integrating technology in Education is the perceptions of the educators. Their views on GenAI are multifaceted, including both positive and negative viewpoints. On one dimension, many teachers recognise the potential benefits of utilising AI tools in enhancing learner education on the other hand, concerns persist in accuracy, and reliability of the generated content, potential over-reliance on technology, ethical challenges related to data privacy and the need for proper training on the effective use of AI tools. These mixed ideas highlight the difficulty in implementing new technologies in educational settings.

Conducting a comprehensive literature review helps to map the current state of research on GenAI in ESL contexts. It enables us to identify the breadth and depth of studies that have examined the benefits and challenges of AI integration, thereby revealing recurring themes, methodological approaches, and notable gaps. By synthesizing past findings, this review not only validates the significance of exploring teacher perceptions but also provides a framework for understanding how educators have responded to these technological innovations over time. This critical evaluation is highly important in informing future research directions and for guiding policy makers and practitioners in developing effective strategies for AI integration in language teaching.

1.1 Research Objectives

The primary objective of this literature review is to explore how ESL teachers perceive the use of Generative AI tools in their classrooms. Specifically, this review aims to:

- 1) Examine the positive perceptions, such as improved instructional efficiency, personalised learning experiences, and enhanced student engagement.
- 2) Investigate the concerns and challenges voiced by teachers, including issues of accuracy, ethical implications, and the need for adequate training.
- 3) Identify gaps in current research, particularly in diverse educational settings, to recommend areas for further study.

1.2 Theoretical Framework

This study is grounded in a multifaceted theoretical framework that integrates the Technology Acceptance Model (TAM), Constructivist Learning Theory, and Mobile Assisted Language Learning (MALL) to clarify teacher perceptions and pedagogical impact of Generative AI (GenAI) tools in ESL classrooms.

1.3 Technology Acceptance Model (TAM)

Technology Acceptance Model (TAM) serves as a foundational framework for understanding how teachers decide to adopt and integrate technology into their teaching practices. Davis describes that the acceptance of new technology is predominantly driven by two factors – “perceived usefulness” and perceived ease of use” [4]. In this context of ESL teaching, if the teachers are aware of the benefits of using technology, for example, update lesson planning, obtain reliable language feedback, and increase student engagement, the teachers will be inclined

to use technology in their classrooms. This model also emphasizes that any issues found in the technical tools can fail in acceptance by the teachers. This study intends to explore how the factors can influence teacher perceptions of GenAI tools, whether they will be accepted as sustainable and resourceful tools for classroom integration.

1.4 Constructivist Learning Theory

As presented by Piaget [5] and Vygotsky [6] learners accumulate knowledge through their experiences in life and reflective practice of the actively learned content. Integration of GenAI tools in their active learning process can provide them with context-rich, interactive authentic exercises. For example, in an ESL classroom, the prompts which are used in a speaking activity can be generated with GenAI tools shaping and molding them at the teacher's and learner's discretion. This promotes language acquisition consistent with constructivist principles. Utilising this concept enables learners to foster deeper understanding and retain language skills, making the learning process engaging and effective.

1.5 Mobile Assisted Language Learning

Mobile Assisted Language Learning (MALL) stresses the importance of accessible, on-demand learning allowing learners to access materials whenever and wherever possible. Utilising GenAI tools in the mobile devices in ESL learning increases the benefits of MALL by providing them with real-life, authentic, personalized language learning exercises and practice outside the traditional language learning classrooms. This continuous learning model aligns with modern educational trends towards flexibility and autonomy, further enhancing the overall learning experience. This research examines how mobile-based GenAI applications can enhance learning beyond the classroom and support a more integrated, lifelong language acquisition process.

As a whole, these three frameworks provide a comprehensive setting in examining teacher perceptions of GenAI in ESL settings. The factors that influence technology adoption in ESL settings are examined with TAM, while the possibility of creating an engaging and authentic experiential learning environment is highlighted by Constructivist Learning Theory [5]. MALL is utilized here in examining the importance of mobile technology in making these innovations accessible and effective for continuous language learning. These integrated theoretical frameworks highlight the multi-dimensional impact of GenAI applications on ESL teaching and aids in providing strategies in effective implementation of them in ESL learning and teaching environments.

1.5 Methodology of the Literature Review

In order to examine teacher perceptions on the use of GenAI tools, a systematic approach was adopted in selecting and analysing relevant literature. This review utilises peer-reviewed journal articles, books and conference proceedings published in 2023 and 2024 to represent the recent shifts and developments in the field.

The selection of articles was based on keyword searches in three databases: Google Scholar, Scopus and ELSEVIER. The terms used for the searches were – Generative AI in ESL Teaching, Teacher Perceptions of AI in Education, Teacher Perceptions of Incorporating AI in English Language Teaching. The studies were considered based on their relevance to the research objectives focusing on their empirical findings, theoretical applications and pedagogical implications.

The thematic analysis was based on the major themes such as “teacher attitudes towards GenAI, benefits and challenges of the incorporation of GenAI and the role played by AI tools in AI-assisted language learning. This structured framework can assist in understanding the existing body of knowledge and identifying gaps for future research.

II. Review of Literature

This review synthesizes key themes, including the role of GenAI in ESL teaching, teacher perceptions, pedagogical benefits and challenges, and empirical studies conducted in ESL settings utilising GenAI tools. The

analysis of the existing research section highlights trends, theoretical perspectives, and gaps, providing insights into the evolving role of AI in ESL education.

2.1 The Role of Generative AI in ESL Teaching

Since the arrival of the GenAI tools, the way that they can be incorporated in ESL classrooms has been researched. Several non-empirical studies [7] – [9] have researched the role of GenAI tools in ESL teaching.

Creely [7] highlights several key opportunities that can be obtained from GenAI tools in language learning. In his conceptual analysis he proposed a conceptual model in integrating GenAI tools in language education for language educators and researchers. Although an exact “model” is not detailed, Creely advocates a balanced and ethical approach in utilising AI by synthesising opportunities and challenges of GenAI while addressing its limitations and ethical considerations. This framework supports personalized leaning experiences, dynamic content generation and immediate feedback, aiming at enhancing language acquisition and literacy skills.

In his conceptual exploration, Ironsi [8] offers insights and recommendations on the use of GenAI in English language teaching. GenAI enhances English language learning by providing vivid at the same time relevant content, which aids the learners acquire and use the language more effectively. It can also boost student engagement through interactive and personalized experiences. Furthermore, AI has the ability to adapt lessons to match individual learning styles and needs, providing better learning outcomes.

Liao et al. [9] use a case analysis using the instruction-reply method in order to investigate the potential of integrating GenAI in learning and practice of the four language skills – listening, reading, writing and speaking. They use ChatGPT in this study, providing prompts and analysed the responses. They identified nine core abilities of AI which contribute to language learning as – natural language processing, adaptive learning, speech recognition and synthesis, attention mechanisms, zero-shot learning, pre-trained models, intelligent recommendation, reinforcement learning and cross-lingual learning. These features enable AI tools to deliver personalized feedback, simulate real communication, and offer diverse learning resources and experiences.

Considering the above three research on the role played by GenAI in ESL settings, it is evident that Creely [7] provides a conceptual framework in integrating AI in a balanced manner while respecting ethics. Ironsi [8] highlights practical benefits in enhancing learner engagement and improving outcomes through personalized, varied content. Both the researchers emphasise the need for careful implementation, though Creely [7] is more focused on ethical synthesis, whereas Ironsi [8] is partial towards pedagogical application of AI tools. Liao et al. [9] on the other hand, offer a more empirical approach by identifying nine core AI capabilities. Unlike Creely’s [7] conceptual emphasis and Ironsi’s [8] classroom-level insights, Liao et al. [9] bridge theory and practice through real-time AI instruction. Together these studies present a holistic view of using GenAI in language: Creely [7] outlines the ethical and conceptual framework, Ironsi [8] situates it in pedagogical practice, and Liao et al. [9] demonstrate its functional effectiveness, highlighting the importance of aligning AI capabilities with ethical and learner-centered teaching strategies.

2.2 Teacher Perceptions of Generative AI

A growing body of research highlights the transformative potential of GenAI tools to enhance teaching and learning process, foster learner autonomy and provide adaptive, personalised support to students. Studies by Chung & Jeong [10], Tafazoli [11], AI-khresheh [12], Kalra [13], and Nowavan et al. [14] collectively feature the positive impact of AI powered technologies when thoughtfully integrated into ESL classrooms. These studies highlight how GenAI can support lesson planning, generate engaging content, offer real-time feedback and promote language development beyond traditional classroom boundaries. Align with these findings, the following section explores the positive perceptions and pedagogical advantages of employing GenAI in ESL education.

2.2.1 Positive Perceptions

Chung & Jeong [10] examined perceptions of 134 Chinese preservice teachers (PSTs) on incorporating AI tools in English language teaching. This study found that PSTs were familiar with the selected AI tool – ChatGPT and recognized their desire to have professional development in this area since many lacked a deep understanding of the functions and how they can be utilised to achieve maximum benefit of it. The participants of this study acknowledged that AI can be used in improving grammar and writing skills and noticed its ability to support personalised learning without reducing interest in traditional methods. They further expressed a high level of acceptance toward using AI in teaching, recognising its importance in increasing efficiency, saving time in lesson planning and assessment, and improving students' comprehension of learning materials.

In order to explore the potential of utilising GenAI by English language teachers to overcome challenges in teaching English, Tafazoli [11] conducted a study with 23 participants. The study was conducted as a qualitative case study examining the effectiveness of ChatGPT as a feasible tool in ESL teaching. The study identified several plus points in incorporating ChatGPT as accessibility in high quality materials, inclusivity of every type of students, personalised learning, incorporating enhanced teaching and learning methods and increasing student engagement and motivation.

Another study explored global English language teacher's perceptions of integrating AI tools into ELT (English Language Teaching) through a qualitative design involving 46 participants from 39 countries [12]. Using open-ended questionnaires, the research identified key pedagogical opportunities such as real-time feedback, personalized learning, enhanced student engagement, and support for writing and critical thinking. Teachers also valued ChatGPT's role in helping quieter students to participate more confidently in the classroom activities. Looking forward, teachers advocated for a hybrid ELT model where AI complements traditional instruction, highlighting the need for curriculum redesign, teacher training, and the development of students' digital, critical, and emotional literacies to harness the full potential of AI tools like ChatGPT.

Kalra [13] explored language teacher's perceptions of integrating AI tools in the classroom through a survey of 208 educators. The findings indicated that while most teachers were moderately familiar with AI tools like Grammarly and ChatGPT, only a few use them regularly. The participants have recognised the potential of AI tools to enhance engagement, personalise learning, and provide immediate feedback. The majority of the participants have shown a positive attitude and willingness to adopt AI tools, provided that adequate training and institutional support were in place.

Nowavan et al. [10] in their study explore how Technology Enhanced Language Learning (TELL) is used in language teaching, perspectives of the educators on utilising AI, implication policies, and challenges of it. Seven English language teachers who are using AI tools are included as the participants of this qualitative study. The findings of this study indicated more positive attitudes towards incorporating AI tools in the classroom due to the benefits as enhancing material development, maintaining an engaged and enthusiastic classroom and continuing effective assessments. Further, "a hybrid model" – balancing AI integration with human interaction was encouraged.

Thus, the above studies, highlight numerous positive effects of integrating AI tools such as ChatGPT into English language teaching. A significant benefit identified is the improvement of students' grammar and writing skills through real-time feedback and language modelling features [10], [12]. Another major advantage of AI technologies is the facilitation in personalised learning by adapting to individual student needs, enabling differentiated instruction while maintaining engagement with traditional methods [10] – [13]. The educators in these studies also reported AI tools aid in increased student motivation and participation with AI, encouraging even quieter learners to engage more actively in classroom activities [10] – [14]. Moreover, the studies [10] and [14] inform that integration of AI tools can enhance teaching efficiency by saving time in lesson planning and creating effective assessments. Also, GenAI tools can provide access to high quality learning materials [11], [14],

which are inclusive of diverse learner profiles [11]. This study further claims that AI tools aid in providing enhanced teaching methods.

It is also indicated in the above studies that while a considerable number of teachers are moderately familiar with the AI tools, many informed of positive attitudes and eagerness to adopt them, especially when adequate training and institutional support are given [13], [14]. Two studies also promote hybrid teaching models where AI compliments traditional instruction, emphasizing the need for curriculum redesign and teacher training to fully harness the pedagogical potential of AI tools [12], [14]. Lastly, the importance of continuous professional development was highlighted [10], as many educators seek to deepen their understanding and effective use of AI in language instruction.

2.2.2 Negative Perceptions

In all the above studies, in line with the multiple benefits of AI integration, considerable concerns were also discussed. Al-khresheh [12] suggests several concerns of using chat GPT in ESL classrooms. One main challenge is its inability to capture some essential aspects of language learning - cultural contexts, emotional depth and context specific meanings. Due to its text- based nature, ChatGPT lacks support for oral skills such as pronunciation and listening. Al-khresheh [12] also noted the failure of ChatGPT to simulate spontaneous, real-life communication which is important in improving authentic language use. He further examines the view of many educators - over reliance on ChatGPT and other AI tools, which potentially diminish the students' critical thinking and problem-solving abilities.

Additionally, the use of AI-generated responses may suppress students' creativity, especially in tasks that require original expression. The digital divide poses another challenge, as not all students and teachers have equal access to technology, or the digital skills needed to use it effectively. Finally, the integration of ChatGPT often clashes with existing curricula and reveals a gap in teacher training, underscoring the need for professional development and pedagogical alignment.

Kalra [13] with the number of optimistic views on the use of AI usage in ESL classrooms, observes several concerns among instructors regarding the integration of AI tools in ESL classrooms. Over reliance is one of the primary issues that was observed in her study which hinders the learners' ability to think critically and certain cognitive functions as brainstorming. This encourages plagiarism. Klara's [13] research participants also doubted the reliability of AI generated information, logical arguments and citing. Skepticism on ethical concerns particularly related to data privacy and academic integrity was also highlighted. Furthermore, reluctance in adopting new technologies, unfamiliarity with AI tools and lacking proper training were viewed as negative perceptions. Finally, their doubts about teacher roles in an AI-assisted learning environment were raised.

Certain apprehensions of AI usage despite its' favourable views were given by Nowavan et al. [14] in their study. Predominantly they emphasise the lack of critical reflection, professional development, policy guidance in utilising AI applications. They also highlighted depersonalization (that is limited human connection) in AI solutions, lack of a robust policy framework for ethics and data privacy.

Similarly, the study [10] reveals several concerns among Chinese Pre-service teachers regarding the integration of AI applications. Primarily their concern was on the over dependency on automated support which obstruct learner's creativity and critical thinking abilities. There were also questions on the authenticity of AI-facilitated interactions, observing that GenAI's struggles in replicating cultural and contextual nuances essential for meaningful language learning. Further, the researchers highlighted ethical concerns related to data privacy, issues in academic integrity, and the production of biased or inaccurate information as some of the major concerns of the integration of AI tools in ESL settings. This study further points out the inefficiency of AI applications in supporting language skills as speaking and listening. Finally, the unfamiliarity and lack of understanding on the effective use of AI applications by the language teachers were emphasised.

Liao et al. [9] also in their study highlights limitations of the integration of AI as the production of mechanical and unnatural language, high user proficiency requirements, inconsistent language recognition, and the probable language inaccuracies. Thus, they suggest the need for cautious implementation of AI tools in ESL contexts.

Therefore, it is clear that a range of critical concerns were addressed in the above five studies in the integration of AI tools in ESL teaching and learning environments. One of the common issues discussed in the studies is the over-reliance on AI tools by the learners which results in deteriorating the learner's creativity, critical thinking and problem-solving abilities [12], [13],[10], while encouraging plagiarism [13]. Another major concern which is highlighted is the failure of AI tools (particularly tools as ChatGPT) in supporting essential language skills such as speaking, listening and spontaneous, real-life communication skills which are essential in authentic language skills [12], [10]. The limitations in replicating cultural nuances, emotional depth and indicating context-specific meanings continue to limit the efficacy of AI tools in creating meaningful interactions in language learning [12], [10]. Reliability of the content including data privacy issues, academic integrity and ethical concerns have been extensively discussed by Kalra [13], Chung & Jeong [10] and Nowavan et al. [14]. Also, lack of familiarity with AI tools, insufficient teacher training, and hesitancy in adopting new technologies are considered as notable barriers in the integration of AI applications in ESL settings [12], [10], [13]. These challenges are intensified due to digital divide as there are disparities in equal access to AI technologies among the ESL educators and learners [12]. Mechanical and unnatural language output, language inaccuracies and inconsistent recognition are also highlighted as limitations of the integration of AI tools. Thus, careful implementation is suggested [9]. Lastly, the lack of powerful policy guidance and ethical frameworks further add to complicate the incorporation of AI in ESL context [14]. Therefore, the above concerns highlight the necessity of professional development, ethical safeguards and pedagogical alignment in confirming AI technologies collaborate rather than impede ESL teaching and learning.

III. Discussion

This paper analysed the emerging role of Generative AI (GenAI) applications in ESL (English as a Second Language) education, focusing on pedagogical applications and teacher perceptions. Our research outlines a picture of the benefits and challenges experienced by ESL educators in their teaching and learning process during the past year. The literature revealed that with the many rewards of the incorporation of GenAI tools in enhancing ESL instruction as personalised learning, obtaining real-time feedback, high efficiency in lesson planning and development of adaptive teaching/learning materials, support for differentiated instruction which increases student engagement and enthusiasm, thereby fostering learner autonomy.

However, the review also marks critical concerns of the integration of GenAI in ESL environments. The educators are troubled by the potential over-reliance on AI tools which may weaken the learners' essential cognitive skills as creativity, critical thinking and problem-solving abilities. The review also highlights the suppression of original expression and increased tendency for plagiarism particularly related to writing activities. Moreover, the ineffectiveness of GenAI to effectively support speaking and listening skills, along with its limitations in capturing cultural and contextual nuances, decreases its effectiveness in supporting holistic language competence. Concerns related to the accuracy and bias of the AI-produced content, data privacy, academic integrity and the digital divide further adds to the issues of GenAI tools which result in further delaying the integration of it in the ESL classrooms.

Another recurring theme is the readiness of the teachers to adopt AI tools. While many educators demonstrate a willingness to use GenAI, the lack of adequate training and institutional support is a major barrier. Teachers require ongoing professional development to navigate ethical considerations, maximize pedagogical benefits, and align AI integration with curriculum goals.

In addition, concerns about the redefinition of teacher roles in AI-assisted environments indicate a need for clearer frameworks that position GenAI as a supportive, rather than a replacement tool in education.

The reviewed studies also emphasise the importance of a hybrid teaching model, where AI is used to complement traditional methods. This approach helps preserve the human element in language teaching which is essential for addressing emotional, cultural, and interpersonal dimensions of learning while leveraging the strengths of GenAI to enhance instructional effectiveness.

IV. Limitations

This research shows that teachers mainly used AI for lesson planning and materials development, with minimal use in assessment and real-time classroom activities. This narrow focus may fully capture the broader potential of AI in language learning. Secondly, this study is based on current perceptions and practices. It lacks long-term data showing how AI integration impacts language proficiency over time. The participants of this study possess limited experience in the full potential of the AI tools; thus, the effectiveness of AI is constrained by the user's lack of expertise or understanding. Additionally, the studies considered for this research are mainly of Asian, Arabian and Austronesian. Therefore, the results may not be generalizable to other contexts with different technological infrastructure, pedagogical cultures or policy environments. Although this review acknowledges concerns such as depersonalisation and the need for ethical guidelines, it does not deeply explore these issues or propose concrete solutions. The focus of this study is mainly on teachers' perceptions. A lack of direct input from students overlooks critical insights into how learners experience and perceive AI in language education.

Furthermore, this study focusses mainly on the AI application – ChatGPT. However, considering the rapid pace of AI development, there are numerous other AI applications which can benefit ESL education. Finally, the number of articles selected for this study is limited to the past couple of years and depending on the perspectives of the educators only. This can result in lack of triangulation.

V. Suggestions

Given the evolving nature of GenAI in ESL education, several avenues for future research emerge. More empirical and longitudinal studies are needed to evaluate the sustained impact of GenAI tools on various aspects of language acquisition, including speaking and listening skills. In order to fill the gap in the skills, investigating effective training frameworks that empower teachers to use GenAI ethically and pedagogically is identified as a necessity. Future studies also need to focus on developing robust ethical guidelines and institutional policies to address concerns related to data privacy, academic integrity, and equitable access. Moreover, it is important to explore how GenAI tools can be adapted to better align with learner differences, including proficiency levels, cultural backgrounds and learning preferences. Most importantly, evaluations of the effectiveness of blended teaching models which integrates human interaction and AI assistance can offer insights into sustainable and scalable ESL practices.

VI. Conclusion

The integration of Artificial Intelligence (AI) in language education presents significant opportunities to enhance curriculum design, pedagogy, and assessment practices. This study highlights that while AI is predominantly used by teachers for lesson planning and materials development, its application in classroom instruction and assessment remains limited. Teachers perceive AI as a valuable tool for promoting personalised learning, improving instructional efficiency, and supporting student autonomy. However, the effectiveness of AI in language learning currently is hindered by gaps in teacher and student readiness, including limited critical reflection, lack of professional development and insufficient training in AI tools.

The findings also underscore the importance of maintaining human interaction in the language learning process. Although AI can offer adaptive feedback and personalization, the absence of emotional engagement and

authentic communication may lead to depersonalized learning experiences. Therefore, a balanced approach that combines the strengths of AI with the irreplaceable human element is essential.

To realize the full potential of AI in language education, a comprehensive and ethical framework is necessary. This includes aligning AI integration with curricular goals, developing teacher competencies, rethinking assessment methods, and establishing clear policies on responsible AI use. Ongoing collaboration among educators, policymakers, and technology developers will be vital to ensure AI is implemented in ways that uphold the core values of language learning. As technology continues to evolve, language educators must take the lead in leveraging AI to create inclusive, engaging, and effective learning environments.

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